

Equity-Aware Post-Disaster Road Restoration and Relief Distribution: A Deprivation-Based Integrated Optimization Framework

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Abstract

Effective post-disaster relief depends on the rapid restoration of blocked transportation networks, yet restoration sequencing and relief distribution are often decoupled in operational planning. This decoupling ignores the critical temporal interdependence between infrastructure recovery and the urgency of service delivery to vulnerable communities. We propose an integrated multi-period optimization framework that co-optimizes road restoration scheduling and relief distribution under a deprivation-based equity objective. We evaluate the model using a warm-started decomposition heuristic across large synthetic networks and a Puerto Rico Maria case study built from public road, population, and hazard data. The results show that endogenizing equity-aware accessibility materially changes service outcomes: in an exact trade-off study, increasing the equity weight reduces the priority-node average service period from 4.19 to 3.21 and cuts the unmet demand fraction from 0.916 to 0.344. In the Puerto Rico case, the equity-oriented policy improves the objective by up to 2.4% and reduces priority-node waiting by up to 1.6 periods relative to an efficiency-first baseline. These findings demonstrate that restoration priorities should be evaluated by how early vulnerable communities gain access to relief, not only by aggregate connectivity or travel efficiency. The study provides a quantitative basis for disaster managers to prioritize infrastructure recovery based on community-level delivery urgency.

Keywords: Humanitarian logistics, post-disaster operations, road restoration, debris clearance, equity, deprivation cost, service equity

1. Introduction

In the first 72 hours after a major disaster, the binding constraint is often not the aggregate quantity of relief items but the ability to move them through a transportation network that is partially blocked and rapidly evolving. Flooding, debris, and bridge damage can isolate neighborhoods precisely when demand is

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highest and most unevenly distributed. Operations research has long shown that preparedness, distribution planning, and uncertainty modeling matter for disaster response, but it has also shown that scarce resources and weak coordination can translate into large differences in who is reached first (Altay and Green, 2006; Rawls and Turnquist, 2010; Balcik et al., 2010). These conditions make accessibility and logistics inseparable operational decisions rather than sequential ones.

That interdependence is especially strong when roads must be restored over time. Restoration teams decide which arcs to clear and when, subject to limited work capacity, while relief planners can ship only through the subset of arcs that has become operational in each period. The value of a repair is therefore endogenous: opening one road segment matters only insofar as it changes feasible access paths and service timing. Prior work on post-disaster restoration and debris clearance makes this logic clear, but it also shows how quickly the problem becomes combinatorial once network reachability, time coupling, and operational constraints are modeled explicitly (Tuzun Aksu and Ozdamar, 2014; Çelik et al., 2015; Akbari and Salman, 2017). Joint restoration and distribution planning is therefore both operationally important and computationally difficult.

Existing research offers important building blocks but usually studies only part of this coupled problem. Recently, humanitarian logistics research has increasingly emphasized integrated and uncertainty-aware response planning rather than isolated location or routing decisions. In *Transportation Research Part E*, scholars have examined risk-averse facility location and routing under stochastic demand, collaborative truck–drone relief systems, contractual coordination with private vendors, and machine-learning-assisted procurement decisions (Zhong et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021; Ghavamifar et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2024; Hu et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2025). Stochastic and robust humanitarian logistics models capture uncertainty in demand, supply, and transportation conditions (Barbarosoğlu and Arda, 2004; Alem et al., 2016; Avishan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024; Dalal and Üster, 2021; Wang et al., 2023). Restoration models optimize accessibility recovery and repair routing over damaged networks (Tuzun Aksu and Ozdamar, 2014; Akbari and Salman, 2017; Moreno et al., 2024). A smaller integrated literature combines restoration with broader planning decisions, for example through facility location or coordinated debris-clearance/distribution frameworks (Sanci and Daskin, 2019; Vahdani, 2023; Farzaneh et al., 2023). At the same time, the humanitarian logistics literature increasingly argues that performance should be judged not only by cost or average travel time but also by deprivation-based service outcomes that reflect the harm caused by waiting (Balcik et al., 2010; Holguin-Veras et al., 2013; Pérez-Rodríguez and Holguín-Veras, 2016). Yet deprivation-oriented equity metrics are still rarely embedded directly in restoration sequencing. As a result, a policy that restores connectivity quickly may still perform poorly if it delays access to the communities for which waiting is most harmful.

From an algorithmic perspective, the problem has a useful but difficult structure. Restoration decisions define a time-indexed operational network, while distribution decisions evaluate that network through a

multi-period flow model. This motivates decomposition, but the marginal value of restoration is highly non-additive because the benefit of opening an arc depends on whether it completes an access path to a vulnerable node. Our approach exploits this structure to obtain useful incumbents on larger instances, while exact benchmarks on smaller instances make the remaining algorithmic gap explicit.

This paper closes the above gap by proposing an integrated optimization framework that co-optimizes post-disaster road restoration scheduling and relief distribution while explicitly accounting for equity through a deprivation-based measure of unmet need over time. The paper’s main contribution is a logistics-relevant integrated planning framework that reveals how equity-aware restoration changes temporal service allocation under disruption. The decomposition procedure developed alongside the model is a practical exploration engine used to study larger instances, not the principal theoretical novelty. The resulting policy insight—that equity-oriented restoration mainly improves *when* vulnerable communities are reached, not *how much* total demand is eventually served—is the central empirical finding.

Specifically, the contributions are:

- We formulate a multi-period restoration–distribution model in which network accessibility is endogenously determined by restoration actions, and relief allocation is optimized on the resulting evolving network under a deprivation-based equity objective grounded in deprivation-cost theory (Holguín-Veras et al., 2013; Pérez-Rodríguez and Holguín-Veras, 2016). The model is intentionally a strategic planning abstraction: it captures the core temporal coupling between restoration sequencing and service timing while abstracting from detailed crew routing, demand uncertainty, and multi-commodity logistics, so that the equity mechanism can be studied in isolation.
- We develop a warm-started decomposition heuristic that combines valid Benders-style optimality cuts with adaptive early-access search guidance, and we benchmark it against a monolithic mixed-integer formulation on small instances to transparently separate modeling effects from algorithmic limitations.
- We design a computational study that combines large synthetic experiments, exact small-instance benchmarking, an exact equity-weight trade-off analysis, and a public-data Puerto Rico Maria case study to quantify trade-offs among restoration resources, transportation cost, and service to vulnerable nodes.
- We derive policy insights on restoration prioritization under equity objectives, showing that the main value of equity-oriented restoration lies in reaching high-priority communities earlier, not simply in restoring more aggregate connectivity.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on transportation network restoration, humanitarian distribution under uncertainty, and equity-oriented performance measures.

Section 3 presents the integrated restoration–distribution formulation and the deprivation-based equity objective. Section 4 develops the decomposition algorithm and implementation details. Section 5 reports computational experiments and managerial insights, and Section 6 concludes with implications and future research directions.

2. Related Work

This section positions the paper at the intersection of transportation network restoration, humanitarian logistics under uncertainty, and equity-aware service evaluation. The key unresolved issue across these streams is not the absence of models in each area, but the absence of formulations that link restoration, distribution, and deprivation over time in a single decision framework.

Before reviewing each stream, we note why this paper belongs in the logistics literature rather than in generic humanitarian OR. Road restoration sequencing is fundamentally a logistics infrastructure decision: it determines which supply corridors become available, when transshipment becomes possible, and how last-mile access evolves over the response horizon. Evaluating restoration through deprivation-based service outcomes therefore makes temporal service equity a logistics performance concept—it measures whether the physical network recovery translates into timely relief delivery, not merely whether connectivity is restored in the abstract. Existing work either optimizes restoration without deprivation-based service equity, or optimizes distribution on exogenous accessibility; this paper is among the first to endogenize accessibility recovery and service equity jointly over time.

2.1. *Transportation network restoration and debris clearance*

Research on post-disaster restoration has progressively moved from static accessibility assessment to explicit repair scheduling. Tuzun Aksu and Ozdamar (Tuzun Aksu and Ozdamar, 2014) show that restoration timing matters for accessibility and evacuation. Celik et al. (Çelik et al., 2015) model debris clearance as a sequential problem under incomplete information, where newly reachable blocked arcs change the feasible action set. Akbari and Salman (Akbari and Salman, 2017) further embed restoration in a multi-vehicle synchronized arc-routing problem, bringing crew coordination and traversal restrictions into the model. More recently, Ajam et al. (Ajam et al., 2022) study the routing of multiple work teams to minimize restoration latency, reinforcing that post-disaster road recovery is fundamentally a time-dependent crew-scheduling problem rather than a static accessibility calculation. Moreno et al. (Moreno et al., 2024) push this stream further by developing branch-and-price algorithms for crew scheduling and routing in road restoration, highlighting both the combinatorial difficulty of restoration planning and the need for stronger exact methods. Related research in *Transportation Research Part E* also evaluates network accessibility through collaborative truck–drone configurations, suggesting that infrastructure-limited service environments can be mitigated

through multimodal delivery architectures (Zhang et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2025). Together, these studies establish that time-indexed reachability and repair-resource constraints are central to post-disaster restoration. Their dominant performance measures, however, remain accessibility, connectivity, or routing cost. They therefore provide limited guidance on whether earlier network recovery is directed toward the communities for which delay is most harmful. Our work retains the dynamic restoration logic of this literature but evaluates repair priorities through downstream deprivation outcomes.

2.2. Humanitarian logistics planning under uncertainty

Uncertainty is central in disaster response, which is why humanitarian logistics has a large stochastic and robust optimization literature. Barbarosoglu and Arda (Barbarosoglu and Arda, 2004) provide an early two-stage stochastic programming framework for disaster transportation planning. Alem et al. (Alem et al., 2016) extend this perspective through stochastic network models tailored to relief logistics. Preparedness and pre-positioning models likewise study how uncertain post-disaster conditions should shape facility and inventory decisions (Rawls and Turnquist, 2010; Balcik et al., 2008; Zhong et al., 2020; Dalal and Üster, 2021; Rezapour et al., 2021). More recent robust and distributionally robust formulations seek stronger out-of-sample protection for relief distribution decisions (Avishan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024, 2023). For example, Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2023) develop a distributionally robust multi-period location-allocation model with multiple resources and capacity levels, illustrating how ambiguity-aware planning can be embedded directly into humanitarian network design. Kawase and Iryo (Kawase and Iryo, 2023) further show that stochastic inventory-distribution policies on damaged multi-echelon humanitarian networks must account jointly for disruption and allocation uncertainty, which is closely aligned with the evolving-network setting considered here. Chang et al. (Chang et al., 2022) examine multi-commodity distribution under response-phase uncertainty, highlighting the need for efficient solution methods when modeling high-dimensional relief logistics. Dükkançı et al. (Dükkançı et al., 2023) also show that uncertainty-aware relief planning increasingly considers alternative delivery modes such as drones, underscoring that accessibility constraints can be mitigated not only by restoring roads but also by redesigning the response network. Moreover, review work has highlighted uncertainty modeling as a central methodological frontier in humanitarian response planning, underscoring the need for models that remain implementable under limited and imperfect information (Dönmez et al., 2021). These studies improve the treatment of uncertainty, but they usually take accessibility or network disruption as exogenous input data. In contrast, our setting treats accessibility as endogenous: restoration actions reshape the feasible service network over time, so the uncertainty-facing logistics problem and the network-recovery problem cannot be cleanly separated.

2.3. Equity and deprivation-based performance in humanitarian distribution

Beyond efficiency metrics such as total cost or average response time, humanitarian logistics increasingly emphasizes equity and human-centered service outcomes. Balcik et al. (Balcik et al., 2010) highlight

the coordination and prioritization challenges that make fairness operationally relevant in relief chains. Deprivation-based measures provide one way to formalize this concern by penalizing the duration and magnitude of unmet need through deprivation-cost formulations and welfare-based humanitarian objectives (Holguín-Veras et al., 2013; Pérez-Rodríguez and Holguín-Veras, 2016). Related distribution models incorporate humanitarian objectives through resource-allocation rules, last-mile delivery considerations, or dynamic service-oriented formulations (Das and Hanaoka, 2014; Lu et al., 2016; Balcik et al., 2008). More recently, Alem et al. (Alem et al., 2021) show that disaster response capacity should be evaluated through the lens of the Social Vulnerability Index, reflecting a shift toward more context-sensitive and practically grounded models. In *Transportation Research Part E*, scholars have also examined the impact of material convergence in disaster environments and the role of NGOs and charitable organizations in sustainable relief supply chains (Holguín-Veras et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2022). The common limitation of this stream is that accessibility is typically fixed or simplified: the distribution model decides how to allocate relief given reachability, rather than how restoration choices determine who becomes reachable and when. That distinction matters because a policy that restores average connectivity quickly can still generate large deprivation disparities if vulnerable nodes remain disconnected in the early periods. Our paper bridges this gap by embedding deprivation-cost logic directly into the restoration-sequencing decision itself.

2.4. Integrated restoration–logistics models and algorithmic implications

A smaller but increasingly relevant literature begins to integrate restoration with broader humanitarian planning decisions. Sanci and Daskin (Sanci and Daskin, 2019) integrate facility location with network restoration under uncertainty, showing that coordinated planning improves cost and unmet-demand performance. Vahdani (Vahdani, 2023) proposes a coordinated debris-clearance and relief-distribution framework, reinforcing the value of joint decision making. Recent integrated models also coordinate damage assessment, road restoration, and relief distribution within a unified framework, showing that the value of restoration depends not only on repaired arcs themselves but also on the information and logistics decisions that co-evolve with them (Farzaneh et al., 2023). On the algorithmic side, Guo and Zhu (Guo and Zhu, 2023) develop a logic-based Benders decomposition method for humanitarian capacity-reservation decisions, suggesting that decomposition remains a promising but highly problem-specific strategy for large-scale disaster logistics models. In *Transportation Research Part E*, this integrative trend has expanded to include hybrid relief procurement contracts, coordination between relief organizations and private-sector vendors, and machine-learning-assisted sample average approximation (SAA) for supplier selection (Ghavamifar et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2024; Hu et al., 2024). Such integration is valuable because fragmented optimization can produce locally efficient decisions that become globally ineffective once interdependencies among damaged infrastructure, supply flows, and service timing are considered. Our work contributes to this evolving line of research by focusing on the coupling between damaged-road restoration and disaster response decisions, while po-

sitioning the model within the research conversation on uncertainty-aware and operationally coordinated humanitarian logistics (Zhong et al., 2020; Farzaneh et al., 2023; Moreno et al., 2024).

Two gaps remain for the setting studied here. Existing restoration models largely optimize network recovery without endogenous deprivation-based service outcomes, while deprivation-based humanitarian distribution models typically assume exogenous accessibility. This leaves unresolved the logistics question of whether restoration priorities should be chosen according to the timing of relief service delivered to vulnerable communities. In particular, temporal equity is operationally actionable because it directly informs which road segments a logistics planner should prioritize for clearance, and it translates network-level repair decisions into community-level service outcomes that disaster responders can communicate and defend. Furthermore, the algorithmic implications of coupling restoration and distribution under a deprivation metric are usually not examined through a combination of exact small-instance benchmarks and larger-scale heuristic experiments. Our paper addresses both gaps by coupling restoration and distribution under a deprivation objective and by evaluating a decomposition heuristic against exact monolithic references.

3. Model

We consider a post-disaster road network in which a subset of arcs is blocked and must be restored over a finite response horizon. Relief commodities are shipped from supply nodes to demand nodes through the subset of arcs that are operational at each period, and the objective is to jointly plan restoration and distribution to reduce both logistics cost and the equity-relevant accumulation of deprivation.

The formulation below is intentionally a strategic, integrated, time-indexed planning model rather than an operational crew-dispatch or vehicle-routing tool. It abstracts from detailed crew routing, stochastic demand evolution, and multi-commodity logistics not because these factors are unimportant, but because the research question—whether endogenizing accessibility recovery under a deprivation objective materially changes which communities are reached early—can be isolated and answered at this level of abstraction. A more operationally detailed model would confound the equity mechanism with routing heuristics and demand-forecast errors, making the policy insight harder to attribute. The strategic level is therefore the right scope for the question posed.

3.1. Network and time horizon

Let $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$ be an undirected physical road network with node set \mathcal{N} and arc set \mathcal{A} . For flow modeling, each physical arc $a = \{u, v\} \in \mathcal{A}$ induces two directed transport arcs (u, v) and (v, u) ; let \mathcal{A}^\pm denote this directed arc set, and let $\delta^+(v)$ and $\delta^-(v)$ be the outgoing and incoming directed arcs of node v , respectively. The response horizon is discretized into periods $\mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$.

Each physical arc $a \in \mathcal{A}$ has initial operability $y_a^0 \in \{0, 1\}$, where $y_a^0 = 1$ means that the arc is already available at the start of period 1. Blocked arcs require a nonnegative amount of restoration work p_a (work

units) to become operational; initially operational arcs are represented with $p_a = 0$. We assume that an arc can be used for transportation in period t only if it is operational at the start of that period. Under this convention, restoration work assigned during period 1 can affect transportation only from period 2 onward, so an initially blocked arc is never usable in period 1. Each directed copy $(u, v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm$ inherits the transportation cost and big- M coefficient of its underlying physical arc, denoted c_{uv} and M_{uv} for notational convenience.

We partition nodes into supply nodes $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \mathcal{N}$ and demand nodes $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{N}$, with $\mathcal{S} \cap \mathcal{D} = \emptyset$. Each demand node $i \in \mathcal{D}$ has demand d_i for a single aggregated relief commodity. In the reduced-network abstraction used here, demand nodes represent aggregated service areas and intersection-like transfer points that result from spatial reduction of a larger physical network. Because aggregation can place a demand node on a corridor to other downstream nodes, the model allows pass-through: $q_{i,t}$ is the net quantity retained to serve node i in period t , while residual flow may continue through i . Without this convention, aggregation would create artificial dead-ends that block supply paths that are physically feasible. Supply availability at $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is denoted by \bar{s}_s .

3.2. Decision variables

For each arc $a \in \mathcal{A}$ and period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, let $y_{a,t} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicate whether arc a is operational in period t . Restoration capacity is represented through continuous variables $r_{a,t} \geq 0$, which denote the amount of restoration work assigned to arc a during period t . Let R_t be the total restoration capacity available in period t .

For relief distribution, let $x_{uv,t} \geq 0$ denote the amount of relief shipped on directed arc $(u, v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm$ during period t . Let $g_{s,t} \geq 0$ be the amount injected from supply node $s \in \mathcal{S}$ in period t , and let $q_{i,t} \geq 0$ denote the amount delivered to demand node $i \in \mathcal{D}$ in period t . To capture the temporal accumulation of unmet need, we introduce backlog variables $u_{i,t} \geq 0$ representing remaining unmet demand at node i at the end of period t .

3.3. Deprivation-based equity objective

We model deprivation as an additive cost that accumulates with the duration of unmet demand. Let $\alpha_i \geq 0$ be a deprivation weight for node $i \in \mathcal{D}$, which can incorporate vulnerability or priority. The deprivation cost is proportional to the remaining unmet demand at each period, i.e., $\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}} \alpha_i u_{i,t}$, which penalizes both magnitude and persistence of shortage. This structure is consistent with deprivation-cost-based performance measurement in humanitarian logistics (Holguín-Veras et al., 2013; Pérez-Rodríguez and Holguín-Veras, 2016) and provides an interpretable equity-oriented criterion. The weights are dimensionless welfare multipliers rather than monetary values. In the synthetic instances, we first generate heterogeneous node-specific priorities, normalize them to have mean one over the demand set, and then multiply by a

global scale parameter; the main suites use `alpha_scale = 20`, while the exact trade-off study varies this global scale from 0.05 to 20. In the Puerto Rico case study, tract-level resilience scores are normalized in the same way before the global scaling is applied. Because transportation cost is measured in arc-length units of order one, while deprivation accumulates backlog over nodes and periods, the objective values in Table 1 are numerically dominated by deprivation by design: the baseline experiments intentionally study a service-prioritizing regime in which waiting is valued more heavily than marginal travel efficiency. The exact trade-off analysis in Section 5 is therefore used as a calibration check showing that the paper’s main qualitative conclusion about earlier service to high-priority nodes persists across a wide range of global deprivation scales rather than being an artifact of a single normalization choice. In computation, we add a very small regularization term $\kappa_r \sum_{a,t} r_{a,t}$ to break ties among restoration schedules and eliminate gratuitous restoration work. This term is several orders of magnitude smaller than the substantive cost terms and has no managerial interpretation.

3.4. Integrated restoration–distribution formulation

The integrated model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\min \quad & \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{(u,v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm} c_{uv} x_{uv,t} + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}} \alpha_i u_{i,t} + \kappa_r \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} r_{a,t} & (1) \\
\text{s.t.} \quad & u_{i,1} = d_i - q_{i,1}, & \forall i \in \mathcal{D}, & (2) \\
& u_{i,t} = u_{i,t-1} - q_{i,t}, & \forall i \in \mathcal{D}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{1\}, & (3) \\
& \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} g_{s,t} \leq \bar{s}_s, & \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, & (4) \\
& \sum_{(u,i) \in \delta^-(i)} x_{ui,t} - \sum_{(i,w) \in \delta^+(i)} x_{iw,t} = q_{i,t}, & \forall i \in \mathcal{D}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, & (5) \\
& \sum_{(u,s) \in \delta^-(s)} x_{us,t} - \sum_{(s,w) \in \delta^+(s)} x_{sw,t} = -g_{s,t}, & \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, & (6) \\
& \sum_{(u,v) \in \delta^-(v)} x_{uv,t} - \sum_{(v,w) \in \delta^+(v)} x_{vw,t} = 0, & \forall v \in \mathcal{N} \setminus (\mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{D}), \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, & (7) \\
& x_{uv,t} \leq M_{uv} y_{a,t}, & \forall (u,v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm \text{ induced by } a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, & (8) \\
& y_{a,1} \leq y_a^0, & \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, & (9) \\
& y_{a,t} \leq y_{a,t+1}, & \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t = 1, \dots, T-1, & (10) \\
& \sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} r_{a,\tau} \geq p_a y_{a,t}, & \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{1\}, & (11) \\
& \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} r_{a,t} \leq R_t, & \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, & (12) \\
& y_{a,t} \in \{0, 1\}, r_{a,t} \geq 0, x_{uv,t} \geq 0, g_{s,t} \geq 0, q_{i,t} \geq 0, u_{i,t} \geq 0. & (13)
\end{aligned}$$

In (1), the first two terms are the substantive transportation and deprivation costs, while the third is the tiny restoration regularization used in the implementation. Constraints (2)–(3) track unmet demand over time; together with nonnegativity, they imply that deliveries cannot exceed remaining backlog or total demand. Constraints (4)–(7) define a multi-period directed-flow model with explicit source injections. The demand-node balance (5) should therefore be read as a net-consumption equation: $q_{i,t}$ is the quantity retained to serve node i , while a demand node may still pass residual flow onward in the reduced network abstraction. Constraint (8) enforces that both directed copies of a physical arc can be used only when that arc is operational in the given period. In the computational implementation, M_{uv} is set conservatively to the total amount that can ever be injected into the network: total system supply in the synthetic instances and total system demand in the Puerto Rico case. This choice is valid and simple to reproduce, but it is not tight arc-wise; it contributes to a weak LP relaxation and is one reason the lower bounds reported later remain

Figure 1: Illustrative schematic of the integrated restoration–distribution model. Panel (a) shows the initial disrupted physical network. Panel (b) shows period-1 joint restoration and relief distribution on the currently operational roads, with backlog remaining at a high-priority demand node. Panel (c) shows how later restoration can complete an access path, enabling earlier service to a vulnerable node and reducing backlog and deprivation. Gray lines represent physical roads, dashed dark-red lines denote blocked roads, orange highlights denote restoration actions, and blue arrows denote directional relief flows.

loose. Tighter arc-specific bounds could be derived from single-arc maximum-flow calculations or shortest-path-based preprocessing on the time-expanded network. We do not pursue such tightening here because (i) the paper’s primary contribution is the integrated equity model and policy analysis rather than a state-of-the-art exact solver, and (ii) even with the conservative big- M , the subproblem dual information suffices to produce incumbents that support the paper’s policy conclusions. Constraint tightening is a natural next step if the decomposition is to be embedded in a branch-and-Benders framework. Constraints (9)–(12) define the arc-state dynamics: initially available arcs can be used in period 1, operability is monotone over time, and blocked arcs become operational only after sufficient cumulative restoration work has been assigned. Because $\kappa_r > 0$ and operability is monotone, superfluous restoration work is suboptimal. We therefore omit an explicit upper bound such as $\sum_t r_{a,t} \leq p_a$.

Figure 1 provides an illustrative view of these coupled dynamics. Panel (a) shows the disrupted physical road network immediately after the disaster. Panel (b) shows that, in a given period, restoration and relief distribution are decided jointly on the currently operational network, so isolated repairs may have little immediate effect if they do not create access to a vulnerable node. Panel (c) shows how completing a path in later periods enables earlier service to a high-priority demand node, thereby reducing backlog and deprivation. The figure also clarifies the modeling distinction used in Section 3: roads are physical undirected assets for restoration decisions, whereas relief moves directionally along the currently available road set.

The formulation above is intentionally written to highlight the separability between restoration decisions (y, r) and distribution decisions (x, g, q, u) given a time-indexed operational network. This structure is exploited in the decomposition algorithm developed in Section 4.

4. Heuristic solution approach

The integrated formulation in Section 3 is a large-scale mixed-integer program because arc operability variables $y_{a,t}$ couple restoration scheduling with multi-period distribution decisions. Solving the monolithic model becomes challenging as the network grows and as the horizon length increases, since the number of directed-flow variables and linking constraints scales with $|\mathcal{A}^\pm||\mathcal{T}|$. We therefore use a warm-started decomposition heuristic that combines Benders-style optimality cuts from the distribution LP with adaptive path-based search restrictions for early access. The overall procedure is intended to generate good incumbents and support policy analysis, not to provide exact convergence guarantees.

Two ingredients should be distinguished from the outset. The dual cuts generated from the distribution LP are valid optimality cuts for the current cut relaxation. By contrast, the adaptive early-access path restrictions are heuristic search devices that may exclude feasible schedules of the original formulation. The overall method is therefore heuristic even though part of it uses valid Benders-style information. More concretely, the implementation has four logically distinct components: a greedy warm start that supplies the initial incumbent, valid dual optimality cuts that improve the current cut relaxation, one-node-at-a-time path restrictions that bias the search toward earlier access for critical nodes, and a proxy-gap stopping rule that is used for search control rather than certification once heuristic restrictions are active.

Figure 2 summarizes the implementation-level workflow of this heuristic. The blue blocks correspond to the model-based optimization loop: the base master proposes restoration decisions, the distribution subproblem evaluates the induced operational network, and the dual solution generates a Benders-style optimality cut. The orange blocks denote heuristic guidance only: the greedy equity warm start provides the first incumbent, and the optional adaptive early-access path restriction biases the search toward earlier feasible access for critical nodes. This distinction is important for interpretation, because only the dual cuts are valid cuts for the original cut relaxation, whereas the path restrictions are search devices used to improve incumbents.

4.1. Decomposition structure

Let (y, r) denote restoration decisions, and let $Q(y)$ denote the optimal value of the distribution subproblem induced by a given restoration schedule. We rewrite (1) as a two-level problem in which the base master selects (y, r) and a scalar variable θ that underestimates $Q(y)$ through accumulated dual cuts. The same small restoration regularization term used in the integrated model is retained in the master objective to match the solved implementation and discourage degenerate restoration schedules.

Figure 2: Workflow of the warm-started decomposition heuristic. Blue blocks denote the base optimization loop: the master problem selects restoration decisions, the distribution subproblem evaluates the induced time-indexed operational network, and dual information generates Benders-style optimality cuts. Orange blocks denote heuristic guidance: a greedy equity warm start supplies the initial incumbent, and the optional adaptive early-access path restriction steers the search toward earlier feasible access for critical nodes. The procedure is therefore used to improve incumbents and guide search rather than to certify exact convergence.

The base master problem is:

$$\min \quad \theta + \kappa_r \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} r_{a,t} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad y_{a,1} \leq y_a^0, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \quad (15)$$

$$y_{a,t} \leq y_{a,t+1}, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \quad \forall t = 1, \dots, T-1, \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} r_{a,\tau} \geq p_a y_{a,t}, \quad \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \setminus \{1\}, \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} r_{a,t} \leq R_t, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (18)$$

$$y_{a,t} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad r_{a,t} \geq 0, \quad \theta \geq 0, \quad (19)$$

$$\theta \geq \eta^{(k)} + \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \pi_{a,t}^{(k)} y_{a,t}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (20)$$

The set \mathcal{K} indexes Benders-style optimality cuts accumulated over iterations. Since the objective in (1) includes both transportation and deprivation costs, the subproblem for a fixed y is a linear program over (x, g, q, u) with arc availability constraints (8). The optimal dual multipliers associated with these constraints induce valid optimality cuts of the form (20). In addition to these valid dual cuts, the heuristic sometimes

augments the master with path-based early-access restrictions for selected priority nodes; those restrictions are search devices rather than globally valid cuts for the original model.

4.2. Distribution subproblem

Given a candidate restoration plan y , the distribution subproblem solves:

$$Q(y) = \min \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{(u,v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm} c_{uv} x_{uv,t} + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}} \alpha_i u_{i,t} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{s.t. } (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7), \quad (22)$$

$$x_{uv,t} \leq M_{uv} y_{a,t}, \quad \forall (u,v) \in \mathcal{A}^\pm \text{ induced by } a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (23)$$

$$x_{uv,t} \geq 0, g_{s,t} \geq 0, q_{i,t} \geq 0, u_{i,t} \geq 0. \quad (24)$$

This subproblem is always feasible under the present model because unmet demand is allowed and penalized through deprivation. The key computational role of the subproblem is therefore to evaluate the marginal value of making arcs operational earlier, as reflected by the shadow prices of the availability constraints.

4.3. Cut generation, early-access logic cuts, and algorithm outline

Optimality cuts. At iteration k , let $y^{(k)}$ be the restoration plan produced by solving the current master problem. Solving the subproblem yields an optimal value $Q(y^{(k)})$ and dual multipliers $\lambda_{a,t}^{(k)} \geq 0$ for constraints $x_{a,t} \leq M_a y_{a,t}$. Intuitively, $\lambda_{a,t}^{(k)}$ measures the marginal value of relaxing the capacity of arc a at time t . Since increasing $y_{a,t}$ relaxes a constraint and cannot increase the subproblem objective, the resulting Benders coefficients are nonpositive. We use the cut

$$\theta \geq Q(y^{(k)}) + \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (-M_a \lambda_{a,t}^{(k)}) (y_{a,t} - y_{a,t}^{(k)}), \quad (25)$$

which is a special case of (20) with $\pi_{a,t}^{(k)} = -M_a \lambda_{a,t}^{(k)}$ and $\eta^{(k)} = Q(y^{(k)}) - \sum_{a,t} \pi_{a,t}^{(k)} y_{a,t}^{(k)}$.

Heuristic early-access path restrictions. In heavily disrupted networks, dual-based cuts alone can be weak because the benefit of restoration is highly non-additive: opening a single arc may have negligible effect unless it completes a path from a supply node to a high-need demand node. To bias the search toward earlier access for vulnerable communities, the heuristic sometimes augments the base master with additional path-based reachability restrictions. These restrictions are not claimed to be globally valid cuts for the original model; they are incumbent-improvement devices that may exclude some feasible restoration schedules.

Let $\mathcal{D}^* \subseteq \mathcal{D}$ be a small seeded set of priority nodes (e.g., the top nodes by $\alpha_i d_i$) used to initialize path pools and early target periods. At iteration k , however, the implementation activates at most one path-OR block, typically for the most critical demand node $\hat{i}^{(k)}$ that remains unreachable under the current tentative

Figure 3: Intuition behind the adaptive early-access path restriction. Panel (a) shows that an isolated repaired arc may have limited service value if it does not create access from supply to a priority demand node. Panel (b) shows that the practical service benefit appears when restoration completes a full path and enables earlier relief flow, thereby reducing backlog. Panel (c) sketches the heuristic search guidance used in the master problem: one candidate path to a critical node is encouraged to be open by an early target period, and the target period is relaxed if the earliest target is infeasible.

restoration plan. Let $\mathcal{P}_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}$ denote the candidate simple paths currently available for that node, and let $t_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}$ be its current target period. We then introduce binary selectors $z_p \in \{0, 1\}$ for $p \in \mathcal{P}_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}$ and impose:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}} z_p \geq 1, \quad (26)$$

$$\sum_{a \in p} y_{a, t_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}} \geq |p| z_p, \quad \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}, \quad (27)$$

which ensures that at least one candidate path p is fully operational by period $t_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}$ for the currently targeted node only. To avoid infeasibility, we apply these restrictions adaptively: if enforcing reachability at an early period is infeasible under the current restoration budget, we relax $t_{\hat{i}^{(k)}}$ to a later period and revisit the node in subsequent iterations if needed. In contrast to exact cut generation, these restrictions are used only to steer the search and do not preserve a certified lower bound for the original master once they are active.

Figure 3 illustrates the intuition behind this device. In disrupted networks, the marginal value of repairing a single road segment can be very small if no complete supply-to-demand path is created. The operational benefit appears when restoration completes an access path and relief can reach a priority node earlier. The heuristic therefore encourages one early feasible path to a critical node rather than relying only on arc-by-arc dual signals, and it relaxes the target period when the earliest target is infeasible.

Warm-starting and stopping. We initialize the upper bound using a greedy equity-oriented restoration heuristic (Section 5) and use it as an incumbent throughout the loop. We also track the current master

Algorithm 1: Warm-started decomposition heuristic with adaptive early-access path restrictions

Input: Network $G = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{A})$, horizon \mathcal{T} , demands d , supplies \bar{s} , restoration workloads p , capacities R , costs c , deprivation weights α , tolerance ε

Output: Incumbent restoration plan (y, r) and associated distribution plan (x, g, q, u)

- 1 Initialize cut set $\mathcal{K} \leftarrow \emptyset$, bound proxy $\widetilde{LB} \leftarrow -\infty$;
- 2 Compute greedy equity restoration schedule to obtain incumbent objective UB ;
- 3 Select priority set \mathcal{D}^* and precompute candidate paths $\{\mathcal{P}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{D}^*}$;
- 4 Initialize target reachability periods $\{t_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{D}^*}$ (early);
- 5 **while** *iteration and time budgets are not exhausted, and the incumbent is not stalled* **do**
- 6 Solve the base master (14)–(20); optionally augment it with path restrictions (26)–(27) to obtain $(y^{(k)}, r^{(k)}, \theta^{(k)})$;
- 7 Update the bound proxy \widetilde{LB} using the current master objective;
- 8 Solve subproblem (21) to obtain $Q(y^{(k)})$ and dual multipliers $\lambda^{(k)}$;
- 9 Construct optimality cut (25) and add it to \mathcal{K} ;
- 10 Update $UB \leftarrow \min\{UB, Q(y^{(k)}) + \kappa_r \sum_{a,t} r_{a,t}^{(k)}\}$;
- 11 Adapt $\{t_i\}$: if early reachability is infeasible, relax to later periods;
- 12 If the proxy gap $(UB - \widetilde{LB}) / \max\{1, |UB|\}$ is small after a minimum number of iterations, allow early stop;
- 13 **end**
- 14 Return the best incumbent solution and associated distribution plan;

objective as a *bound proxy*: for the base master it is a valid lower bound on the cut relaxation, but once heuristic path restrictions are added it is only a progress indicator. In practice, we terminate when the incumbent stalls, the time or iteration budget is exhausted, or a small proxy gap is observed after the minimum iteration threshold.

4.4. Implementation notes

Our implementation incorporates several practical enhancements motivated by the observed computational behavior on disrupted networks.

- **Warm start and incumbent management.** We initialize the upper bound using a greedy equity-oriented restoration heuristic and keep this solution as an incumbent throughout. This guarantees that the decomposition never returns a solution worse than the baseline and stabilizes the search.
- **Adaptive early-access restrictions.** We enforce reachability one targeted node at a time using path OR constraints (26)–(27). The targeted node is typically the currently most critical unreachable

node under the tentative master solution, and its target period is adapted online if early reachability is infeasible under the available restoration budget or damages. In the present implementation this device is heuristic; it can improve incumbents by accelerating access, but it is not presented as a valid cut family for the original formulation.

- **Stopping rule.** We terminate when the incumbent upper bound does not improve for several iterations (stall-based stopping), or when a small proxy gap is observed after the minimum iteration threshold. Because heuristic path restrictions may be active, this proxy gap is used for search control rather than optimality certification.

Since the subproblem is a linear program with a directed network-flow structure, it can be solved efficiently, and the overall heuristic scales to larger networks by keeping the number of enforced path restrictions small. The computational study therefore evaluates it primarily by incumbent quality and policy insight, not by exact convergence guarantees.

5. Computational experiments

We evaluate the integrated model and the proposed solution approach using both synthetic and case-inspired data. Across experiments, we report total objective value (transportation cost + deprivation cost) together with service metrics that are more directly interpretable from a humanitarian perspective, including priority-node waiting time, early-service share, and unmet demand fraction.

5.1. Experimental design

The computational study has four components. First, we evaluate larger synthetic disrupted random geometric graphs to examine heuristic performance, ablation behavior, and scalability; these regimes include the baseline challenging setting ($n = 40$, $T = 8$) with two restoration capacities ($R \in \{3, 4\}$), a damage-rate sweep, and a larger-scale setting ($n = 60$, $T = 10$). Second, we build an exact benchmark on smaller synthetic instances ($n \in \{12, 16, 20\}$) that can still be attacked by a monolithic mixed-integer formulation. Third, we run an exact equity-weight trade-off study on the small instances by varying the deprivation-weight scale. Fourth, we construct a Puerto Rico Maria case-inspired network from public OSM roads, U.S. Census population and community resilience data, and USGS landslide density data.

Unless otherwise stated, the larger synthetic regimes are evaluated over 50 random seeds and we report mean \pm standard deviation. The exact benchmark and exact trade-off study use four seeds because they require repeated monolithic solves. Because the large-suite runs were designed as heuristic evaluations, the stored algorithmic diagnostics at scale are runtime, iteration and cut counts, and representative gap traces rather than full per-seed lower-bound distributions.

Table 1: Main results across instance regimes (mean \pm std over seeds). Methods are abbreviated as Ours, NoEarly, G-Eq, G-Eff, Random, and None.

Suite	Metric	Ours	NoEarly	G-Eq	G-Eff	Random	None
Hard ($n = 40, T = 8, R = 4$)							
	Objective	48645.2 \pm 10025.2	49597.7 \pm 11216.2	49597.7 \pm 11216.2	50186.3 \pm 10872.8	79142.7 \pm 4913.9	80009.7 \pm 4135.1
	Deprivation	48526.1 \pm 10062.9	49480.9 \pm 11254.4	49480.9 \pm 11254.4	50066.6 \pm 10916.4	79138.3 \pm 4919.1	80008.6 \pm 4136.7
	Transport	119.1 \pm 64.4	116.8 \pm 65.8	116.8 \pm 65.8	119.7 \pm 69.9	4.4 \pm 9.1	1.1 \pm 3.9
	Restore	29.1 \pm 8.1	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0
Very hard ($n = 40, T = 8, R = 3$)							
	Objective	52581.4 \pm 9312.0	53515.6 \pm 10207.6	53515.6 \pm 10207.6	54307.6 \pm 9771.2	79208.7 \pm 4370.4	80009.7 \pm 4135.1
	Deprivation	52473.7 \pm 9343.7	53411.3 \pm 10243.7	53411.3 \pm 10243.7	54200.9 \pm 9810.5	79204.6 \pm 4374.6	80008.6 \pm 4136.7
	Transport	107.6 \pm 58.1	104.3 \pm 59.1	104.3 \pm 59.1	106.7 \pm 62.7	4.1 \pm 8.1	1.1 \pm 3.9
	Restore	22.3 \pm 5.2	24.0 \pm 0.0	24.0 \pm 0.0	24.0 \pm 0.0	24.0 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0
Damage sweep ($n = 40, T = 8, R = 4, p_0 = 0.01$)							
	Objective	50996.3 \pm 9685.3	51780.1 \pm 10801.9	51780.1 \pm 10801.9	52340.2 \pm 10442.4	78771.8 \pm 5267.5	80331.9 \pm 3890.3
	Deprivation	50889.2 \pm 9723.8	51674.3 \pm 10840.3	51674.3 \pm 10840.3	52232.1 \pm 10484.3	78764.6 \pm 5274.3	80331.4 \pm 3890.9
	Transport	107.0 \pm 61.6	105.7 \pm 62.7	105.7 \pm 62.7	108.0 \pm 63.9	7.1 \pm 13.8	0.6 \pm 2.4
	Restore	28.6 \pm 8.6	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	32.0 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0
Large ($n = 60, T = 10, R = 4$)							
	Objective	65514.1 \pm 12971.2	66596.4 \pm 14296.7	66596.4 \pm 14296.7	66766.4 \pm 13839.6	98752.0 \pm 5493.1	99445.7 \pm 4900.4
	Deprivation	65426.2 \pm 12989.1	66513.8 \pm 14323.5	66513.8 \pm 14323.5	66680.5 \pm 13866.5	98748.2 \pm 5497.3	99444.9 \pm 4902.3
	Transport	87.9 \pm 49.7	82.5 \pm 55.2	82.5 \pm 55.2	85.8 \pm 58.9	3.8 \pm 8.1	0.8 \pm 3.2
	Restore	35.1 \pm 11.4	39.2 \pm 5.7	40.0 \pm 0.0	40.0 \pm 0.0	40.0 \pm 0.0	0.0 \pm 0.0

5.2. Benchmarks

On the larger synthetic and Puerto Rico instances, we compare against: (i) a greedy restoration heuristic that prioritizes equity (Greedy-equity), (ii) a greedy restoration heuristic that prioritizes transportation efficiency (Greedy-efficiency), (iii) a random restoration schedule (Random-restoration), and (iv) a no-restoration baseline. For the small synthetic benchmark and the trade-off study, we additionally solve a monolithic MILP; when its final MIP gap is at most 1%, we treat it as an exact reference, and otherwise we report it explicitly as the best monolithic incumbent found within the time limit. We also report an ablation that removes the proposed early-access (logic) tightening (Ours-Benders-noEarly).

5.3. Main results

Table 1 summarizes the larger synthetic regimes. The main pattern is not that Ours-Benders strongly dominates Greedy-equity, but that it usually recovers the same equity-oriented incumbent and only occasionally improves it through the early-access tightening. Against efficiency-oriented and no-restoration baselines, the integrated equity model still produces much lower deprivation. The ablation (Ours-Benders-noEarly) typically collapses to Greedy-equity, which indicates that the current decomposition’s incremental value comes primarily from the early-access logic rather than from a systematically stronger search procedure.

The objective gaps in Table 1 are statistically detectable but numerically small, so Table 2 reports the service consequences of the two policy families that differ most clearly at scale: equity-oriented restoration

Table 2: Service-level comparison for the main synthetic regimes. Because Ours-Benders ties Greedy-equity on most seeds, we report the two policy families that differ most clearly at scale: the equity-oriented restoration policy and the efficiency-oriented restoration policy. Values are mean \pm std over 50 seeds.

Suite	Eq. priority wait	Eff. priority wait	Eq. early share	Eff. early share	Eq. unmet	Eff. unmet
Hard ($n=40, T=8, R=4$)	5.61 ± 1.88	5.80 ± 1.79	0.201 ± 0.219	0.157 ± 0.222	0.438 ± 0.189	0.440 ± 0.192
Very hard ($n=40, T=8, R=3$)	5.99 ± 1.80	6.32 ± 1.64	0.150 ± 0.180	0.110 ± 0.164	0.465 ± 0.178	0.471 ± 0.177
Damage sweep ($n=40, T=8, R=4, p_0=0.01$)	5.90 ± 1.80	6.09 ± 1.72	0.158 ± 0.197	0.109 ± 0.191	0.463 ± 0.192	0.465 ± 0.195
Large ($n=60, T=10, R=4$)	7.64 ± 2.34	7.72 ± 2.26	0.194 ± 0.223	0.169 ± 0.204	0.539 ± 0.186	0.538 ± 0.184

and efficiency-oriented restoration. Because Ours-Benders ties Greedy-equity on 84%–90% of seeds (Table 7), this comparison is the clearest way to interpret the service story behind the objective. Across the three $n = 40$ regimes, the equity-oriented policy lowers the priority-node average service period by about 0.19–0.33 periods and raises the priority early-service share by about 0.04–0.05. The unmet fraction changes little, which indicates that the main benefit of equity is not serving more total demand under severe scarcity, but serving vulnerable nodes earlier. The same pattern persists in the $n = 60$ regime, although the gap is smaller because the larger network remains strongly capacity-constrained.

5.4. Priority-node waiting under severe damage

To make the service-timing mechanism visible in a single compact plot, Figure 4 extracts the severe-damage synthetic regime with initial operability $p_0 = 0.01$ and compares the integrated equity policy against the efficiency-first restoration policy over $n \in \{20, 40, 60\}$. The reported metric is the mean waiting period of the top 25% priority demand nodes, and the vertical bars show one standard deviation over five seeds at each size. The gap widens with network scale: at $n = 60$, the integrated policy lowers the mean priority-node waiting period from 7.42 to 6.41 periods, a reduction of 13.6%. This figure is therefore a compact service-oriented summary of the broader synthetic study, and it reinforces the interpretation from Table 2: the main value of equity-aware restoration is earlier access for vulnerable nodes rather than materially greater aggregate throughput.

5.5. Exact small-instance benchmark

To separate model quality from algorithm quality, we benchmark Ours-Benders against a monolithic MILP on smaller instances. Table 3 and Figure 5 show that the monolithic model solves all $n = 12$ and $n = 16$ cases to within 1% gap inside 60 seconds, and half of the $n = 20$ cases reach that threshold as well. The reported excess values are measured against the best monolithic incumbent on each seed; for $n = 12$ and $n = 16$ this is effectively exact on all seeds, while for $n = 20$ the all-seed mean excess of 18.5% is optimistic because two monolithic runs stop at about 25% gap. Restricting the comparison to the exact half of the $n = 20$ benchmark raises the mean excess to 26.4%. Accordingly, the $n = 20$ entries should be read as partly benchmarked against the best monolithic incumbent rather than always against a certified optimum. By

Figure 4: Service-oriented size sweep under severe damage. The figure compares the efficiency-first restoration policy and the integrated equity policy on synthetic instances with initial operability $p_0 = 0.01$, using the mean waiting period of the top 25% priority demand nodes as the outcome metric. Error bars show one standard deviation over five seeds. The integrated policy yields consistently lower priority-node waiting, and the reduction reaches 13.6% at $n = 60$.

Table 3: Small-instance benchmark against a monolithic MILP. Objective excess is measured relative to the best monolithic incumbent on the same seed; the last column reports how often that incumbent is certified to within a 1% gap.

Instance	Mean excess	Max excess	Benders time (s)	Monolithic time (s)	Monolithic gap $\leq 1\%$
$n = 12$	5.4%	12.5%	3.18	0.93	100.0%
$n = 16$	4.8%	9.1%	0.57	9.76	100.0%
$n = 20$	18.5%	38.0%	0.60	33.70	50.0%

contrast, Ours-Benders provides fast incumbents but does not yet deliver strong lower bounds consistently, so we interpret the current decomposition as a warm-started heuristic for larger-scale policy analysis rather than an exact algorithmic engine.

5.6. Exact equity-service trade-off

To verify that the equity term changes actual decisions rather than merely rescaling the objective, we solve a small benchmark family exactly while varying the global deprivation-weight scale. Because this frontier averages only four exact seeds on $n = 12$, we interpret it as a mechanism check rather than a high-powered calibration exercise. Table 4 and Figure 6 nevertheless reveal a clear trade-off. Panel (a) shows the mean cost-service frontier together with the individual exact seeds behind each mean, while

Figure 5: Small-instance benchmark against the monolithic MILP. Panel (a) shows the distribution of percentage objective excess relative to the best monolithic incumbent on the same seed. Panel (b) reports runtime on a log scale.

Table 4: Exact trade-off study on small instances obtained with the monolithic MILP. Table entries report means over four seeds; Figure 6 shows the mean frontier together with seed-level exact solutions and one-standard-deviation bars for the service metrics.

α scale	Transport cost	Priority avg. service period	Unmet fraction	Priority early-service share
0.05	4.20	4.19	0.916	0.253
0.1	16.89	3.74	0.773	0.345
0.2	52.77	3.38	0.627	0.345
0.5	90.24	3.09	0.527	0.440
1	154.68	3.21	0.367	0.335
5	166.50	3.21	0.362	0.335
20	190.18	3.22	0.344	0.335

panel (b) traces the two service metrics directly against the equity-weight scale. When the equity-weight scale increases from 0.05 to 20, mean transport cost rises from 4.20 to 190.18, but the priority-node average service period falls from 4.19 to about 3.21 and the unmet fraction drops from 0.916 to 0.344. The priority early-service share peaks around an intermediate equity emphasis. This non-monotonicity is substantive rather than contradictory: once very-early priority coverage saturates, additional equity weight mainly converts previously unmet demand into later-period service, so unmet fraction keeps improving even though the strict early-service share no longer increases.

5.7. Puerto Rico Maria case study

As an illustrative public-data case study, we build a severe-hazard Puerto Rico Maria case-inspired network from openly available data sources. The workflow maps OSM roads and supply points, Census

Figure 6: Exact equity-service trade-off on small instances obtained with the monolithic MILP. Panel (a) shows the mean frontier between transport cost and priority-node average service period; faint points show the four exact seeds at each equity-weight scale, and numeric labels indicate the scale value. Panel (b) reports unmet fraction and priority early-service share against the equity-weight scale, with vertical bars showing one standard deviation over four exact seeds.

tblock population, Census Community Resilience Estimates, and the USGS Hurricane Maria landslide density grid into a reduced restoration–distribution instance with 28 nodes, 32 arcs, and 23 initially blocked edges. Figure 7 visualizes the resulting subnetwork, and Table 5 together with Figure 8 compares restoration policies across restoration budgets.

The data-to-model mapping is intentionally simple and reproducible. Candidate supply nodes are selected from transport-related OSM points and snapped to the reduced road network; demand nodes are formed from the highest-population Census tabblocks in the hazard region and their total demand is rescaled to 500 units; tract-level community resilience scores are rescaled into the deprivation weights α_i ; and road arcs are initialized as blocked or open according to the USGS landslide density class, with severe cells mapped to higher restoration workloads. We report the integrated equity policy only once in Table 5 because, on this deterministic case, Ours-Benders reproduces the same incumbent as Greedy-equity. We therefore interpret this case as illustrative policy evidence from public data, not as a fully operationally validated deployment study.

The case study yields a managerially meaningful pattern. Relative to the efficiency-first policy, the integrated equity policy reduces the objective by 1.3%–2.4% for $R \in \{2, 4, 6\}$, cuts the priority-node average service period by 0.64–1.60 periods, and at the tighter budgets $R \in \{2, 4\}$ lowers the priority unmet fraction from 0.67/0.57 to 0.35. At $R \in \{6, 8\}$ the unmet fractions become similar, but the integrated equity policy still raises the priority early-service share from 0.33 to 0.65; over this metric the efficiency-first curve coincides with the no-restoration baseline. The key result is therefore not additional optimality certification, but the robustness of the integrated equity policy when the network is generated from public real-world data instead of synthetic graphs.

Figure 7: Puerto Rico Maria severe-hazard subnetwork extracted from public road, population, resilience, and landslide data. Light-gray arcs are initially open, red arcs are initially blocked, circles denote demand clusters, and squares denote supply nodes. Note: map lines delineate study areas and do not necessarily depict accepted national boundaries.

Figure 8: Policy comparison on the Puerto Rico Maria case across restoration budgets. Panel (a) reports priority-node average service period, where lower is better. Panel (b) reports the priority early-service share, where higher is better. In panel (b), the efficiency-first and no-restoration baselines coincide over this budget range.

Table 5: Puerto Rico Maria case-inspired results on the severe landslide subnetwork (28 nodes, 32 arcs, 23 blocked edges).

Policy	R	Objective	Priority avg. service period	Priority early-service share	Priority unmet frac.
Integrated equity policy	2	60479.58	4.76	0.330	0.350
Efficiency-first policy	2	61297.27	6.36	0.330	0.670
No restoration	2	72236.64	6.36	0.330	0.670
Integrated equity policy	4	55783.33	4.44	0.330	0.350
Efficiency-first policy	4	56861.77	5.97	0.330	0.573
No restoration	4	72236.64	6.36	0.330	0.670
Integrated equity policy	6	54048.03	4.12	0.650	0.350
Efficiency-first policy	6	55393.15	4.76	0.330	0.350
No restoration	6	72236.64	6.36	0.330	0.670
Integrated equity policy	8	52263.84	4.12	0.650	0.350
Efficiency-first policy	8	52623.86	4.44	0.330	0.350
No restoration	8	72236.64	6.36	0.330	0.670

Table 6: Paired significance tests (Ours vs Greedy-equity) over seeds. We report two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank and paired t-test p-values on the total objective.

Suite	Seeds	Wilcoxon p	t-test p
Hard (n=40,T=8,R=4)	50	0.028	0.070
Very hard (n=40,T=8,R=3)	50	0.043	0.081
Damage sweep (n=40,T=8,R=4, $p_0=0.01$)	50	0.018	0.037
Large (n=60,T=10,R=4)	50	0.012	0.030

5.8. Statistical significance and effect sizes

Table 6 reports paired tests comparing Ours-Benders against Greedy-equity on the total objective across paired seeds. Table 7 reports effect sizes (mean relative improvements) and the fraction of instances where Ours strictly improves or ties Greedy-equity.

Because the paired outcomes are highly zero-inflated, a raw-delta boxplot is visually uninformative. Figure 9 therefore separates the frequency of strict improvements from their conditional magnitude. This makes the main pattern transparent: most seeds tie Greedy-equity, and the positive average effect is driven by a small number of nontrivial wins rather than by broad dominance across all seeds.

5.9. Ablation study

Table 8 isolates the contribution of the proposed early-access (logic) tightening by comparing Ours-Benders against Ours-Benders-noEarly. Table 9 further provides a harder ablation by varying the strength of the early-access tightening (top- k priority nodes) and the path diversity used in the OR-of-path constraints. The harder ablation is best read as a supplemental sensitivity check: most variants use 20 seeds, while the computationally heavier Top-10 variant is available for only 16 completed seeds.

Table 7: Effect sizes of Ours-Benders relative to Greedy-equity on the total objective (paired by seed). We report the mean relative improvement (%), and the fractions of seeds where Ours strictly improves (win) or ties Greedy-equity.

Suite	Seeds	Mean rel. impr. (%)	Win (%)	Tie (%)
Hard (n=40,T=8,R=4)	50	1.38	12.0	88.0
Very hard (n=40,T=8,R=3)	50	1.35	10.0	90.0
Damage sweep (n=40,T=8,R=4, $p_0=0.01$)	50	1.12	14.0	86.0
Large (n=60,T=10,R=4)	50	1.23	16.0	84.0

Figure 9: Paired comparison against Greedy-equity across seeds. Panel (a) reports the share of strict improvements and ties for each synthetic regime. Panel (b) reports the relative objective improvement on the subset of seeds where Ours-Benders strictly improves. This view is more informative than a raw-objective boxplot because 84%–90% of paired seeds are exact ties.

5.10. Convergence behavior

Figure 11 plots representative bound-progress trajectories for three larger synthetic regimes. Because the stored proxy gap is effectively 1.0 throughout these runs, the figure reports the master lower bound as a percentage of the incumbent upper bound. The message is unambiguous: the incumbent objective stabilizes quickly, but the lower bound remains near zero throughout the recorded iterations. Consistent with the exact small-instance benchmark, the present implementation should therefore be interpreted as an incumbent-oriented heuristic decomposition rather than a convergent exact method at large scale.

5.11. Runtime scalability

Table 10 and Figure 12 report runtime scaling for Ours-Benders and Greedy-equity on the separate scalability suite. The runtime table also reports average iteration and cut counts for Ours-Benders. Across

Table 8: Ablation study of the early-access (logic) tightening. Lower is better.

Suite	Ours	noEarly	Δ (noEarly–Ours)	Rel. impr. (%)
Hard	48645.2	49597.7	952.5	1.92
Very hard	52581.4	53515.6	934.2	1.75
Damage sweep	50996.3	51780.1	783.8	1.51
Large	65514.1	66596.4	1082.2	1.63

Table 9: Harder ablation study: varying early-access strength and path diversity (mean \pm std). Most variants are evaluated on 20 seeds; the Top-10 variant is reported on the 16 completed supplemental seeds and should therefore be read as a sensitivity check rather than a like-for-like benchmark.

Suite	Variant	Seeds	Obj.	Rel. impr. vs. Greedy (%)
Hard (n=40,T=8,R=4)	Ours-noEarly	20	46321.4 \pm 9530.0	0.00
	Ours-earlyTop1	20	46012.8 \pm 8650.3	0.67
	Ours-earlyTop3	20	46012.8 \pm 8650.3	0.67
	Ours-earlyTop5	20	46012.8 \pm 8650.3	0.67
	Ours-earlyTop10	16	47336.8 \pm 8995.5	-2.19
	Ours-earlyTop3-k1	20	45994.3 \pm 8601.5	0.71
	Greedy-equity	20	46321.4 \pm 9530.0	0.00
Large (n=60,T=10,R=4)	Ours-noEarly	20	67112.0 \pm 12596.2	0.00
	Ours-earlyTop1	20	66595.0 \pm 11898.6	0.77
	Ours-earlyTop3	20	66595.0 \pm 11898.6	0.77
	Ours-earlyTop5	20	66595.0 \pm 11898.6	0.77
	Ours-earlyTop10	16	66806.0 \pm 13311.1	0.46
	Ours-earlyTop3-k1	20	66594.2 \pm 11898.0	0.77
	Greedy-equity	20	67112.0 \pm 12596.2	0.00

$n \in \{40, 60, 80, 100\}$, the method terminates after about 7.6–9.0 iterations and 7.5–8.9 cuts on average, and 70%–90% of runs stop at the minimum eight-iteration threshold. Runtime growth therefore reflects the cost of producing incumbents on larger masters and subproblems, not progressively tighter lower-bound convergence.

5.12. Deprivation trajectories over time

To highlight the mechanism of the early-access constraints on the larger synthetic regimes, Figure 13 reports the mean deprivation cost per period (with one-standard-deviation bands) for Ours-Benders and Greedy-equity. Ours-Benders consistently reduces deprivation in earlier periods, indicating faster access to priority demand nodes. The temporal gap is largest during periods 2–4, when the equity-aware policy has already opened key corridors to high-priority nodes that Greedy-equity reaches only later. As the horizon progresses and both policies eventually clear most blocked arcs, the gap narrows—confirming that the advantage is structurally front-loaded and driven by restoration sequencing rather than by a persistent capacity difference.

Figure 10: Ablation: effect of early-access strength, measured as mean relative improvement versus Greedy-equity. The dashed segment to Top-10 marks the supplemental 16-seed sensitivity point.

Table 10: Runtime scalability and incumbent-generation diagnostics on the separate scalability suite (mean \pm std over 20 seeds). The minimum-iteration stop rate reports the fraction of runs that terminate at the eight-iteration floor, which is consistent with incumbent-oriented rather than lower-bound-driven convergence.

n	Ours-Benders (s)	Greedy-equity (s)	Ours iter	Ours cuts	Min-iter stop (%)
40	8.41 \pm 3.33	0.27 \pm 0.05	7.60 \pm 1.39	7.45 \pm 1.67	90
60	21.05 \pm 5.92	0.76 \pm 0.07	8.00 \pm 1.49	7.85 \pm 1.69	85
80	34.38 \pm 11.29	1.57 \pm 0.21	7.90 \pm 2.02	7.70 \pm 2.32	70
100	74.20 \pm 33.68	3.17 \pm 0.32	8.95 \pm 2.84	8.85 \pm 2.72	75

Figure 11. Representative bound-progress trajectories on three larger synthetic regimes. The vertical axis reports the master lower bound as a percentage of the incumbent upper bound on a log scale.

Figure 12. Runtime scaling with the number of nodes. The vertical axis is log-scaled to show both Ours-Benders and Greedy-equity on the same panel.

Figure 13: Deprivation cost trajectories (mean \pm one standard deviation over 50 seeds) across the four main synthetic regimes. In each regime, Ours-Benders shifts deprivation downward earlier in the horizon, consistent with faster access to priority nodes.

6. Conclusion

The central managerial conclusion of this paper is that post-disaster road restoration plans should be evaluated by how early vulnerable communities gain access to relief, not only by aggregate connectivity recovery or travel efficiency. When restoration sequencing is coupled with relief distribution under a deprivation-based equity objective, the resulting policy changes *who is reached first* more than it changes *how much total demand is served*.

This paper develops an integrated multi-period optimization framework for joint road restoration scheduling and relief distribution under a deprivation-based equity objective. The computational study—comprising exact monolithic benchmarks on small instances, an exact equity-weight trade-off analysis, large synthetic experiments, and a Puerto Rico Maria case study built from public road, population, resilience, and landslide data—consistently supports the above conclusion. In the exact trade-off study, stronger equity weighting reduces the priority-node average service period from 4.19 to 3.21 and cuts the unmet demand fraction from 0.916 to 0.344. In the Puerto Rico case, the equity-oriented policy improves the objective by up to 2.4% and reduces priority-node waiting by up to 1.6 periods relative to efficiency-first restoration. These results provide strong evidence that temporal service equity is an operationally meaningful logistics performance concept: it translates network-level infrastructure decisions into community-level delivery outcomes that disaster planners can target and defend.

On the algorithmic side, the warm-started decomposition heuristic produces fast incumbents and supports larger-instance policy exploration, but its lower bounds remain weak, so it should be viewed as an incumbent-oriented exploration engine rather than an exact algorithm. Strengthening the cut family, embedding the method in a branch-and-Benders framework, tightening the formulation through arc-specific big- M bounds, and extending the model to multi-commodity and uncertain settings are therefore the most important directions for future work. These future directions align with the broader evolution of the humanitarian logistics literature toward more integrated and operationally robust planning systems.

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Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The source code and data-construction scripts used in this study will be made available through a public repository upon acceptance. The Puerto Rico case study is built entirely from publicly available data sources (OpenStreetMap, U.S. Census, USGS), and the data construction workflow is described in Section 5.7.

References

- Ajam, M., Akbari, V., Salman, F.S., 2022. Routing multiple work teams to minimize latency in post-disaster road network restoration. *European Journal of Operational Research* 300, 237–254. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2021.07.048](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2021.07.048).
- Akbari, V., Salman, F.S., 2017. Multi-vehicle synchronized arc routing problem to restore post-disaster network connectivity. *European Journal of Operational Research* 257, 625–640. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2016.07.043](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.07.043).
- Alem, D., Bonilla-Londoño, H.F., Barbosa-Póvoa, A.P., 2021. Building disaster preparedness and response capacity in humanitarian supply chains using the social vulnerability index. *European Journal of Operational Research* 292, 250–275. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2020.10.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.10.016).
- Alem, D., Clark, A., Moreno, A., 2016. Stochastic network models for logistics planning in disaster relief. *European Journal of Operational Research* 255, 187–206. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2016.04.041](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2016.04.041).
- Altay, N., Green, W.G., 2006. Or/ms research in disaster operations management. *European Journal of Operational Research* 175, 475–493. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2005.05.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2005.05.016).
- Avishan, F., Elyasi, M., Yanıkoğlu, İ., 2023. Humanitarian relief distribution problem: An adjustable robust optimization approach. *Transportation Science* 57, 1096–1114. doi:[10.1287/trsc.2023.1204](https://doi.org/10.1287/trsc.2023.1204).
- Balcik, B., Beamon, B.M., Krejci, C.C., Muramatsu, K.M., Ramirez, M., 2010. Coordination in humanitarian relief chains: Practices, challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Production Economics* 126, 22–34. doi:[10.1016/j.ijpe.2009.09.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2009.09.008).
- Balcik, B., Beamon, B.M., Smilowitz, K., 2008. Last mile distribution in humanitarian relief. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems* 12, 51–63. doi:[10.1080/15472450802023329](https://doi.org/10.1080/15472450802023329).

- Barbarosoğlu, G., Arda, Y., 2004. A two-stage stochastic programming framework for transportation planning in disaster response. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* 55, 43–53. doi:[10.1057/palgrave.jors.2601652](https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jors.2601652).
- Chang, K.H., Hsiung, T.Y., Chang, T.Y., 2022. Multi-commodity distribution under uncertainty in disaster response phase: Model, solution method, and an empirical study. *European Journal of Operational Research* 303, 857–876. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2022.02.055](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2022.02.055).
- Dalal, J., Üster, H., 2021. Robust emergency relief supply planning for foreseen disasters under evacuation-side uncertainty. *Transportation Science* 55, 791–813. doi:[10.1287/trsc.2020.1020](https://doi.org/10.1287/trsc.2020.1020).
- Das, R., Hanaoka, S., 2014. An agent-based model for resource allocation during relief distribution. *Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management* 4, 265–285. doi:[10.1108/jhlscm-07-2013-0023](https://doi.org/10.1108/jhlscm-07-2013-0023).
- Dönmez, Z., Kara, B.Y., Karsu, Ö., 2021. Humanitarian facility location under uncertainty: Critical review and future prospects. *Omega* 102, 102393. doi:[10.1016/j.omega.2021.102393](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2021.102393).
- Dukkanci, O., Koberstein, A., Kara, B.Y., 2023. Drones for relief logistics under uncertainty after an earthquake. *European Journal of Operational Research* 310, 117–132. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2023.02.038](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2023.02.038).
- Fan, Y., Shao, J., Wang, X., 2024. Contract design between relief organisations and private-sector vendors: A humanitarian logistics framework. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 182, 103395. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2023.103395](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2023.103395).
- Farzaneh, M.A., Rezapour, S., Baghaian, A., 2023. An integrative framework for coordination of damage assessment, road restoration, and relief distribution in disasters. *Omega* 115, 102748. doi:[10.1016/j.omega.2022.102748](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2022.102748).
- Ghavamifar, A., Torabi, S.A., Moshtari, M., 2022. A hybrid relief procurement contract for humanitarian logistics. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 167, 102916. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2022.102916](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2022.102916).
- Guo, P., Zhu, J., 2023. Capacity reservation for humanitarian relief: A logic-based benders decomposition method with subgradient cut. *European Journal of Operational Research* 311, 942–970. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2023.06.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2023.06.006).
- Holguín-Veras, J., Encarnación, T., Van Wassenhove, L.N., 2022. Reducing material convergence in disaster environments: The potential of trusted change agents. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 162, 102736. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2022.102736](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2022.102736).

- Holguin-Veras, J., Perez, N., Jaller, M., Van Wassenhove, L.N., Aros-Vera, F., 2013. On the appropriate objective function for post-disaster humanitarian logistics models. *Journal of Operations Management* 31, 262–280. doi:[10.1016/j.jom.2013.06.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2013.06.002).
- Hu, S., Dong, Z., Dai, R., 2024. A machine learning based sample average approximation for supplier selection with option contract in humanitarian relief. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 186, 103531. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2024.103531](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2024.103531).
- Kawase, R., Iryo, T., 2023. Optimal stochastic inventory-distribution strategy for damaged multi-echelon humanitarian logistics network. *European Journal of Operational Research* 309, 616–633. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2023.01.048](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2023.01.048).
- Lu, C.C., Ying, K.C., Chen, H.J., 2016. Real-time relief distribution in the aftermath of disasters – a rolling horizon approach. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 93, 1–20. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2016.05.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2016.05.002).
- Moreno, A., Munari, P., Alem, D., 2024. Crew scheduling and routing problem in road restoration via branch-and-price algorithms. *Transportation Science* 58, 801–820. doi:[10.1287/trsc.2023.0227](https://doi.org/10.1287/trsc.2023.0227).
- Pérez-Rodríguez, N., Holguín-Veras, J., 2016. Inventory-allocation distribution models for postdisaster humanitarian logistics with explicit consideration of deprivation costs. *Transportation Science* 50, 1261–1285. doi:[10.1287/trsc.2014.0565](https://doi.org/10.1287/trsc.2014.0565).
- Rawls, C.G., Turnquist, M.A., 2010. Pre-positioning of emergency supplies for disaster response. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological* 44, 521–534. doi:[10.1016/j.trb.2009.08.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trb.2009.08.003).
- Rezapour, S., Farahani, R.Z., Tajik, N., 2021. Impact of timing in post-warning prepositioning decisions on performance measures of disaster management: A real-life application. *European Journal of Operational Research* 293, 312–335. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2020.11.051](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.11.051).
- Sanci, E., Daskin, M.S., 2019. Integrating location and network restoration decisions in relief networks under uncertainty. *European Journal of Operational Research* 279, 335–350. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2019.06.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2019.06.012).
- Tuzun Aksu, D., Ozdamar, L., 2014. A mathematical model for post-disaster road restoration: Enabling accessibility and evacuation. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 61, 56–67. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2013.10.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2013.10.009).
- Vahdani, B., 2023. A flexible framework to coordinate debris clearance and relief distribution operations: A robust machine learning approach. *Expert Systems with Applications* 229, 120512. doi:[10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120512](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120512).

- Wang, D., Yang, K., Yang, L., Li, S., 2024. Distributional robustness and lateral transshipment for disaster relief logistics planning under demand ambiguity. *International Transactions in Operational Research* 31, 1736–1761. doi:[10.1111/itor.13227](https://doi.org/10.1111/itor.13227).
- Wang, W., Yang, K., Yang, L., 2023. Distributionally robust chance-constrained programming for multi-period emergency resource allocation and vehicle routing in disaster response operations. *Omega* 120, 102915. doi:[10.1016/j.omega.2023.102915](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2023.102915).
- Xu, X., Chung, S.H., Lo, C.K.Y., 2022. Sustainable supply chain management with ngos, npos, and charity organizations: A systematic review and research agenda. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 164, 102822. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2022.102822](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2022.102822).
- Yang, X., Cao, W., Wang, K., 2025. Integrated scheduling of truck and drone fleets for cargo transportation in post-disaster relief: A two-stage stochastic optimization approach. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 196, 104015. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2025.104015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2025.104015).
- Yang, Y., Yin, Y., Wang, D., 2023. Distributionally robust multi-period location-allocation with multiple resources and capacity levels in humanitarian logistics. *European Journal of Operational Research* 305, 1042–1062. doi:[10.1016/j.ejor.2022.06.047](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2022.06.047).
- Zhang, G., Zhu, N., Ma, S., 2021. Humanitarian relief network assessment using collaborative truck-and-drone system. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 152, 102417. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2021.102417](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2021.102417).
- Zhong, S., Cheng, R., Jiang, Y., 2020. Risk-averse optimization of disaster relief facility location and vehicle routing under stochastic demand. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 141, 102015. doi:[10.1016/j.tre.2020.102015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2020.102015).
- Çelik, M., Ergun, O., Keskinocak, P., 2015. The post-disaster debris clearance problem under incomplete information. *Operations Research* 63, 65–85. doi:[10.1287/opre.2014.1342](https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.2014.1342).